

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Integration schemes of RES4LIVE adapted technologies with commercial solutions

Deliverable 2.2

WP2. Market available RES and energy efficiency solutions, machinery and practices for livestock farms

Project title

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	Company/Institution
Author/s	UGENT
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ABBREVIATIONS

B	: Battery electrical storage
COP	: Coefficient of performance
GHG	: Greenhouse gas
HP	: Heat pump
LCC	: Life cycle cost
PV	: Photovoltaic
PVT	: Photovoltaic-thermal
RES	: Renewable energy source
ST	: Solar thermal
TS	: Thermal storage
W	: Wind turbine

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Livestock barns have a high electrical and thermal energy demand, attributed to guaranteeing comfortable conditions and indoor air quality for the animals. Currently, these demands are typically met by extracting electricity from the grid or combusting fossil fuels (oil or gas). Renewable energy sources have already been developed and are being used extensively for residential applications. The cost-effective implementation of the sustainable technologies in livestock farms is however not straightforward. Therefore, in the RES4LIVE project, a numerical model was developed where the use of these technologies can be simulated. The model allows to determine the life cycle cost of the installation and the annual carbon dioxide emissions. It will be used to develop integration schemes of RES technologies for livestock barn. The technologies under consideration are heat pumps, solar energy (photovoltaic panels, thermal solar collectors, and hybrid panels), wind turbines, electric storage and thermal storage.

In order to develop these integration schemes, different types of simulations were performed, where the model was applied to the ILVO reference barn. This farm was selected due to the high amount of information that is available on both the electrical and thermal energy demand. First, six selected systems designs were simulated. These include the current system (without RES and with a gas boiler) and systems with a heat pump, possibly combined with other RES. As can be seen in the figure below, all cases without gas boiler have significantly reduced GHG emissions, but potentially at an increased cost (evaluated by the life cycle cost, LCC).

Next, the considered RES technologies are compared on an individual basis. In the figure below, the example is given of where photovoltaic solar panels (PV) are compared with solar thermal collectors (ST) for a farm with a heat pump. It can be observed that for this case, PV panels are the more interesting choice. This however depends on the demand and on whether or not a heat pump is used.

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As the optimal RES system for a farm will most likely be a combination of different technologies, a design space was defined and completely simulated. Of all these data points, the solutions with the lowest emissions for a given installation cost were selected and investigated. As can be seen below, significant emission reductions are possible with LCC below that of the current system.

In addition to these simulations on the ILVO farms, the results for two other reference farms are presented and also some other energy efficiency measures are simulated.

In conclusion, this deliverable presents a model that allows to optimally design an RES system for a livestock farm. The results indicate that where there is a high heating load, a heat pump will effectively reduce emissions. In any case, solar energy and (for larger installations) wind energy can cost-effectively be used. While thermal storage is economically feasible, electrical storage is less often found in the optimal mix.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Livestock barns have a high electrical and thermal energy demand, attributed to guaranteeing comfortable conditions and indoor air quality for the animals. Currently, these demands are typically met by extracting electricity from the grid or combusting fossil fuels (oil or gas). Renewable energy sources have already been developed and are being used extensively for residential applications. The cost-effective implementation of the sustainable technologies in livestock farms is however not straightforward. Therefore, in the RES4LIVE project, a numerical model was developed where the use of these technologies can be simulated. The model allows to determine the life cycle cost of the installation and the annual greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The technologies under consideration are heat pumps, solar energy (photovoltaic panels, thermal solar collectors and hybrid panels), wind turbines, electric storage and thermal storage. The working principles of the model is discussed in chapter 2.

In chapter 3, the results of various simulations performed with the model are discussed. First, some selected cases are investigated, and the different technologies are compared individually. As the optimal design of an RES solution for any given farm will likely be a combination of different technologies, an optimally sized design can be found for a given energy demand.

The results indicate that the largest reduction in GHG emissions can be achieved with the installation of a heat pump. For the presented case, the most cost-effective design, with still high emission reductions, has a mix of different technologies with a large share of photovoltaic solar panels.

1.1 Disclaimer

In the model, multiple simplifications have been made in order to reduce complexity and to assure generality. Additionally, the model was constructed to reflect the situation at the reference farms (and more specifically the ILVO farm). Finally, cost and emission factors are country dependent. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with care and conclusions cannot necessarily be translated to a different context.

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2 METHODOLOGY

In order to design farms with minimized GHG emissions, a model was developed in Python where the energy performance and GHG emissions (related to using gas or electricity from the grid) of the barn can be simulated for an entire year. The electrical energy demand and thermal energy demand (possibly on different temperature levels) are given as inputs to the model with a resolution of one hour. Also, weather data (outside temperature, solar irradiation, and wind velocities) are provided to the model as input.

Different RES technologies are implemented in the model: heat pumps, solar energy, wind energy, thermal storage, and electrical storage. For every time step of the simulated period, the model compares the energy demand to the renewable energy potential. If the energy demand is greater than the generation potential, electricity is taken from the grid or heat is produced by combustion of gas from the grid. Additionally, electrical, and thermal storage can be used. If the generation potential exceeds the demand, energy can be stored for later.

Based on the energy flows calculated by the model, the total electricity and gas taken from the grid for a barn with a certain RES installation are found. This allows to determine the yearly operational costs (and life cycle costs) and equivalent GHG emissions.

2.1 Reference barn

As the yearly energy demand and the energy demand profile can vary significantly for different farms, the calculations are performed for a reference barn. In this case, the pig farm “Varkenscampus” operated by ILVO in Melle (Belgium) is considered. A picture of this barn can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Picture of the ILVO barn

On the ILVO pig farm, yearly 105 sows, 600 piglets and 750 finishing pigs are kept. The barn has an electricity demand of approximately 107 MWh/y and a heat demand of 212 MWh/y. For this barn accurate energy demands per month and per year are available. Additionally, a realistic heat demand profile was developed earlier [1]. This profile is available for a low temperature heat demand (underfloor heating at 40°C) and a high temperature heat demand (air heating at 70°C). More information about the energy demand of the barn is given in Annex A.

2.2 Considered technologies

Several renewable energy technologies were identified in Deliverable 2.1 [2]. A selection of these technologies was implemented in the model based on their market availability and potential of GHG

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emission reductions. The technologies are heat pumps, photovoltaic solar panels (PV), thermal solar collectors (ST) and photovoltaic-thermal solar panels (PVT), horizontal axis wind turbine energy, electrical energy storage (batteries) and hot water thermal energy storage.

For each of these technologies, a model was implemented in Python describing its performance and cost. The level of detail in these models was deliberately kept low in order to minimize calculation time. Furthermore, higher levels of detail require multiple assumptions and input data, which are not always available and often only have a small impact on the results. To compensate for the reduced level of detail, a sensitivity analysis was performed on the results.

All details regarding the modelling of the considered technologies are described in Annex A. This includes the modelling of the performance and the cost functions.

2.3 Control strategy

As the electrical and thermal energy demand are considered known and supplied to the model, the control strategy of the simulations is rather straightforward.

Generated energy (electrical and thermal) is first maximally used on site. When there is an excess of energy generation, this is maximally stored. When electrical storage is at full capacity, electricity is injected into the grid. As no thermal grid is considered, any excess heat is discarded. When solar and wind energy are not sufficient to cover the loads, the energy deficit is taken from the grid.

More complex control is needed when heat is supplied at two different temperatures (e.g., on the ILVO farm, underfloor heating occurs at 40°C, while air heating is done with water at 60°C). Some choices need to be made when the thermal energy generated by the ST or PVT panels is not sufficient to cover the heat load at both temperatures, or when the power that can be delivered by the storage tank is not sufficient. In this case, the user of the model can assign a priority to the heat load at one of both delivery temperatures. In the simulations in this report, the low temperature heat demand was given priority.

2.4 System evaluation

In the previous sections, the working principles of the model and the different submodels was explained. It was discussed how the investment costs of the different technologies are calculated and how the energy flows are determined. Based on the energy taken from (or injected in) the electricity and gas grid, also operational costs and equivalent GHG emissions can be determined.

These GHG emissions are a first parameter on which different system design are compared. In this model, GHG associated with combustion of gas from the grid or the use of electricity from the grid are taken into account. The assumed emission factors of both can be found in Table 5 in Annex A.

The second parameter is the life cycle cost (LCC) of a system, which takes into account both investment costs and operation costs. The LCC is calculated according to Eq. 1:

$$LCC = IC_0 + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{EC_i + IC_i}{(1+r)^i} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. 1, IC_0 represents the investment costs made at the beginning of the simulated period (€), i is the considered year, EC_i are the energy costs in year i (€), n is the simulated period (year) and r is a

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discount rate. As the expected life span of some technologies could be less than the simulated period, the investment cost of a certain technology is added to the LCC when the life span is exceeded. This is captured with the term IC_i (€).

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3 RESULTS

With the model in place, different system design can be compared in order to develop integration schemes for RES technologies. In this chapter, different approaches will be used to examine which technologies can minimize both GHG emissions and LCC. As many parameters need to be specified, an overview of all parameters used in this chapter (called the *Base case parameters*) can be found in Annex A.2.

In the first step (section 3.1) some specific cases will be simulated and compared. The individual use of different technologies will be evaluated (section 3.2). Next, an entire design space will be simulated, allowing to identify optimal solutions and discover trends in the results (section 3.3). Finally, an optimization algorithm will be used to find the best solution for a given budget (section 3.4).

3.1 Selected system designs

In this section, a selection of 6 different cases will be compared. The first case is the current system installed on the ILVO reference farm, consisting of only a gas boiler. As the goal is to minimize GHG emissions, all other cases will use a heat pump, possibly combined with solar or wind energy. A heat pump is used because it is assumed that the emissions related to using electricity (either generated locally or taken from the grid) are lower than those of using gas. The emissions factors can be found in Table 5 in Annex A. The different cases are:

- Case 1: Gas boiler without RES (System currently installed)
- Case 2: One high temperature heat pump (55 kW) and one low temperature HP (15 kW)
- Case 3: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of PV panels
- Case 4: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of solar thermal panels (ST)
- Case 5: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of PVT panels
- Case 6: Same as Case 2 with the addition of a 15 kWn wind turbine

An area of 500m² was selected because this is approximately what is available on the ILVO barn.

In Figure 2, the resulting LCCs and GHG emissions are shown, relative to the LCC and emissions of Case 1. This case has an LCC of €642000 and GHG emissions of 77 ton/y (not shown in Figure 2).

It can be observed that all cases have significantly lower GHG emissions than the current system. Only a heat pump results in a reduction of 50.3%, while the maximal reduction is obtained in the combination with PVT panels (62.9% reduction).

The LCC of all cases is similar to the LCC of Case 1 (-7.2% to +16.3%). Case 3, with heat pumps and PV panels, has the lowest LCC, while Case 4, with heat pumps and solar collectors has the highest LCC.

It can be concluded from this comparison that significant GHG emission reductions are possible compared to the current situation. This can even be done with a reduced LCC. The systems here are however not yet optimally sized and don't combine different RES in one system. This is combination of different technologies is discussed in the next sections.

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Figure 2: LCC and GHG emissions of the selected cases, relative to Case 1.

3.2 Individual RES comparison

In this section, some RES technologies are compared on an individual basis. The best use of the available roof area is investigated (photovoltaic, solar thermal panels or PVT) and the preference for use of wind or solar energy. As the goal of minimise fossil fuel use in livestock farming, the results discussed in this section are for solutions including a heat pump. Results for the same farm without a heat pump (gas boiler heating) are given in Annex D.

In Figures 3 and 4, photovoltaic panels (PV) are compared with solar collectors (ST) and PVT panels (PVT). Both GHG emission reduction and LCC are given for a range of available roof areas. The graphs allow to compare using either only one technology (left and right sides of the graph) or a combination of two technologies (x-values larger than 0 and smaller than 1). On the right graphs, the black dashed line represents the LCC of the original installation without RES (only a gas boiler).

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Figure 3: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and solar collectors (0: all ST, 1: all PV).

Figure 4: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and PVT panels (0: all PVT, 1: all PV).

It can be seen from the left graphs in Figures 3 and 4 that all the technologies have the potential to reduce the GHG emission. A larger installation (increase in used area) will always result in increased reductions. PVT panels result in the largest reductions (Figure 3, left), closely followed by PV panels. The potential of solar thermal collectors to reduce emissions is in this case significantly lower. Regarding the cost (seen on the right graphs of Figures 3 and 4), PV panels seem to be most interesting and will in all cases result in the lowest LCC (where $A_{PV}/A_{used}=1$). While PVT panels can result in a lower LCC than the original design indicated with the dashed line (except for the largest installation), solar thermal collectors will always have an LCC higher than the original design.

Next, the use of wind energy is compared to the use of solar energy. As the results from Figures 3 and 4 showed, PV panels have a high GHG emission reduction and the lowest LCC, so PV will be used here. The possible GHG emission reduction and the associated LCC are shown in Figure 5. Since only a single type of wind turbine (with a nominal power output of 15 kW) is implemented in the model, the results

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below are for one, two or three of these turbines. The results show that for the lowest investments, both PV and wind turbines perform similar. Large emission reductions are possible and the LCC is for all cases lower than for the original installation. For larger installations, the GHG emission reductions are higher with wind turbines, however, so are the life cycle costs.

Figure 5: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and one to three wind turbines.

Instead of looking at PV panels and wind turbines individually, a combination of both was also investigated. Figure 6 shows the GHG emission reduction, and the life cycle costs for installations with a given cost. The different lines indicate how many wind turbines (of 15 kWn each) were assumed, while the remaining budget is spent on PV panels. The cost of the heating system (heat pumps in this case) is not included in the installation cost. Including one or more wind turbines in the design can clearly contribute to reduced emissions. The LCC is however lowest for RES installations with only PV panels (except for installations with a cost higher than €186600).

Figure 6: GHG emission reduction and life cycle cost for a combination of PV panels and wind turbines.

The same comparison as presented in this section was also done for a design with a gas boiler instead of a heat pump. These results are presented in Annex D. The main difference lies in the fact that instead

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of solar thermal collectors become more interesting for GHG emission reduction than photovoltaic panels, but PVT are most interesting. PV panels however still result in the lowest LCC.

3.3 Design space exploration

In previous sections, the use of different RES technologies was investigated individually. It is however likely that the optimal system design consists of a combination of all technologies. Therefore, a design space was defined using the technologies and possible sizes as listed in Table 1. The combination of all possibilities results in 165888 possible designs.

Table 1: Design space definition for the ILVO reference farm.

Parameter	Possible values	Count
Heating system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gas boiler (60 kW) High temperature heat pump (60 kW) High temperature heat pump (55 kW) + low temperature heat pump (15 kW) 	3
PV panel area (m ²)	0, 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	8
Solar collector area (m ²)	0, 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	8
PVT panel area (m ²)	0, 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	8
Battery capacity (kW)	0, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200	6
Thermal storage volume (l)	0, 250, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	6
Wind turbine nominal power (kW)	0, 15, 30	3

This entire design space was simulated, with the base case parameters as defined in Section 2. An overview of the results is given in Figure 7, where the annual GHG emissions for a given design are represented as a function of the investment cost of that design. The colour of the points indicates the relative difference between the LCC of a design compared to the LCC of the current installation (gas boiler, no RES). For clarity, only designs with an investment cost below €500000 are shown. The design of the current installation, with only a gas boiler and no RES technologies, is represented by the upper left point (minimal installation cost and maximal GHG emissions).

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Figure 7: Overview of the results of the design space exploration for the ILVO reference barn.

The results in Figure 7 show a clear distinction in two *clouds* of data points, with emissions below and above approx. 40000 kg/y. All data points contained in the upper cloud represent designs without a heat pump, using a gas boiler for heating, while points in the lower cloud all use one or two heat pumps. As the purchase cost of a heat pump is higher than that of a gas boiler, the lower cloud starts at higher installation costs than the upper cloud. It can be seen that RES significantly reduce GHG emissions, as the introduction of a only a heat pump already decreases the emissions by almost 50%. Additionally, it can be seen that by introducing RES, the LCC can either increase (LCC difference > 0%) or decrease (LCC difference < 0%), compared to the installation without RES. Using only a heat pump (without other RES) has an LCC that is 5.5%. The introduction of other sustainable technologies generally decreases the LCC. According to the simulations of the design space, when using a heat pump, a total investment of € 112000 is required to achieve a lower LCC than the current design. With even higher investments in RES, LCC reductions of more than 20% are possible. These however require (for the case where heat pumps are used), upfront investments of at least € 252000.

In order to get a better idea of what (combination of) solutions appear to be ideal, all Pareto-optimal solutions (lowest GHG emissions for a given installation cost) from Figure 7 are selected and shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that for most price ranges, a solution can be designed where the GHG emissions are lower than the original emissions, with also a reduced LCC. Only for installation costs between approx. €65000 and €112000, the solution with the lowest emissions would have a higher LCC. This is because using a heat pump without or with limited amount of other RES significantly reduces GHG emissions but appears to be not very cost-effective. This data was analysed and the prevailing technologies (for the optimal solutions with a reduced LCC) are indicated on the graph.

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Figure 8: Pareto optimal solutions for designs with either a lower or a higher LCC than the original installation, with indication of the type of RES used.

3.4 Design optimization

In the previous sections, all systems in a discrete space were simulated. For the comparison in this section, an optimization algorithm (implemented in the Python SciPy-library) was used on the model. When given a certain budget, this algorithm tries to find the “best” solution as a (continuous) combination of all implemented technologies. The “best” solution can be defined as systems resulting in the least GHG emissions (section 3.4.1) or in the lowest LCC (section 3.4.2), while in section 3.4.3, a comparison of both optima is made.

3.4.1 Optimization for minimal GHG emissions

A first optimization is done where the solver tries to find the design with the lowest GHG emissions. The results for installation costs between €16000 and €400000 can be seen in Figure 9 for an installation without a heat pump and Figure 10 for an installation with a heat pump. It can be observed that with a gas boiler (Figure 9), the largest part of the remaining budget goes to PVT panels or thermal solar collectors (ST). Only a small share of the budget is reserved to include photovoltaic panels (PV), wind energy (W), battery electrical storage (B) and thermal storage (TS) in the mix. This is in contrast with the results for the case with a heat pump (Figure 10). Here, the largest share of the money is spent on PV panels and wind energy.

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Figure 9: Optimization of the RES system for a given budget for the case with a gas boiler with minimal GHG emissions as the goal (HP: Heat pump; PV: Photovoltaic panels; ST: Solar thermal collectors; PVT: Photovoltaic-thermal; W: Wind turbine; B: Battery; TS: Thermal storage).

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Figure 10: Optimization of the RES system for a given budget for the case with a heat pump with minimal GHG emissions as the goal (HP: Heat pump; PV: Photovoltaic panels; ST: Solar thermal collectors; PVT: Photovoltaic-thermal; W: Wind turbine; B: Battery; TS: Thermal storage).

3.4.2 Optimization for minimal LCC

The solver can also be used to optimize the design in order to minimize the life cycle cost (instead of the GHG emissions). The results for these calculations can be seen in Figures 11 and 12. For the case without a heat pump (Figure 11), it is now mainly PV and wind that are included in the mix. PVT and solar thermal (that were the primary choice in Figure 9) are only included with higher budgets. It can be noted that the maximal investment is limited to approx. €210000. This indicated that the LCC cannot be decreased with investing in additional RES technologies. This is not the case for a design with a heat pump, as the maximal investment cost (€400000) is equal to the maximal budget. It appears that the LCC can incrementally be decrease by adding more PV. The results for the heat pump are similar to the designs optimized for minimal GHG emissions, especially for the lowest budgets.

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Figure 11: Optimization of the RES system for a given budget for the case with a gas boiler with minimal LCC as the goal (HP: Heat pump; PV: Photovoltaic panels; ST: Solar thermal collectors; PVT: Photovoltaic-thermal; W: Wind turbine; B: Battery; TS: Thermal storage).

Figure 12: Optimization of the RES system for a given budget for the case with a heat pump with minimal LCC as the goal (HP: Heat pump; PV: Photovoltaic panels; ST: Solar thermal collectors; PVT: Photovoltaic-thermal; W: Wind turbine; B: Battery; TS: Thermal storage).

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3.4.3 Comparison of different optimizations

Finally, the optimal solutions for the previous pictures are compared in Figures 13 and 14.

In Figure 13, where the GHG emissions of all optimal designs that can be found. The blue designs are systems with a gas boiler, while the orange designs include a heat pump. As could be expected, the designs with a heat pump have significantly lower GHG emissions. Interestingly, it can be observed that for most cases, designs that were optimized for minimal LCC have GHG emissions very close to designs that were optimized for emissions.

The LCC of all optimal solutions is shown in Figure 14. For installation costs below €200000, designs with a gas boiler can always have an LCC lower than design with the same cost incorporating a heat pump. Above that budget, solutions with a heat pump can be more interesting. It can also be noted that for high budgets, significantly larger LCC is required to marginally decrease emissions further.

Figure 13: Comparison of GHG emissions of optimized designs for given budgets, with and without a heat pump.

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Figure 14: Comparison of LCCs of optimized designs for given budgets, with and without a heat pump.

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4 OTHER REFERENCE FARMS

The simulations presented above were all performed for the ILVO reference farm. Within the RES4LIVE project, 3 other reference farms are considered. A brief overview of integrated solutions for these farms will be presented next.

4.1 Farm introduction

The Golinelli farm is a commercial pig farm in Italy with an occupancy of approximately 500 sows and 2500 weaners. No simulations were performed for this farm since insufficient energy demand data was available.

The experimental dairy farm of LVAT is located in Gross Kreuz (Germany) and includes three barns for milk production with an overall occupancy of 455 animals. In total, the farm has an electricity use of approximately 270 MWh/y and a heating demand (met by combustion of LPG) of 30 MWh/y.

Finally, the AUA farm is an experimental poultry farm in Athens (Greece). This is the smallest of the pilot farms with room for approximately 850 chickens. The farm has a yearly electricity demand of approximately 14 MWh and no heating system is present.

More information about the farms and the energy demand can be found in deliverable 3.1 [3].

4.2 Simulation results

As for the Golinelli farm, insufficient data is available, no results are presented here.

4.2.1 LVAT farm

The LVAT farm was implemented in the model, the electrical and thermal energy load were averaged over each month. The resulting electrical demand for the barn is 282.6 MWh, while the total thermal demand is 29.4 MWh. Solar panels yield 946.6 kWh/kWp, while one wind turbine (with a nominal power of 15 kW) annually generates 22.4 MWh. According to the model, the current installations on the farm result in GHG emissions of 69.6 ton/y and a life cycle cost over 20 years of €1018996.

For the LVAT farm, a similar analysis was performed as section 3.3 for the ILVO farm, where an entire design space was simulated. The possibilities for each type of RES are given in Table 2. In total, 27648 designs were simulated. The heating system in the model represents the LPG boiler present in the current farm and used for heating of the working areas related to milk production.

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Table 2: Design space definition for the LVAT reference farm.

Parameter	Possible values	Count
Heating system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gas boiler (30 kW) High temperature heat pump (30 kW) 	2
PV panel area (m ²)	0, 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	8
Solar collector area (m ²)	0, 10, 100, 1000	4
PVT panel area (m ²)	0, 10, 100, 1000	4
Battery capacity (kW)	0, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200	6
Thermal storage volume (l)	0, 250, 500, 1000, 2500, 5000	6
Wind turbine nominal power (kW)	0, 15, 30	3

The resulting data (for designs with an installation cost below €500000) can be found in Figure 15. It can be observed that within this installation cost, the GHG emissions can be reduced with 62.6% (to 26 ton/y). For most of the Pareto-optimal designs (lowest emissions for a given installation costs), the obtained LCC is lower than the current LCC.

Figure 15: Overview of the results of the design space exploration for the LVAT reference barn.

When the data is investigated in more detail, it was observed that most of the optimal designs employ a heat pump. Since only a heat pump of 30 kW is required for this barn (instead of 60 kW for the ILVO barn), the investment in this technology is significantly lower. However, since the thermal demand is only 9.4% of the total energy demand (where this was 66.5% for the ILVO barn), the potential of a heat pump to reduce the emissions is much lower, and no two distinct “clouds” of points can be observed.

Because of this high electrical demand, the amount of PV panels is maximised by the model, while PVT and solar thermal panels are less involved in optimal designs. From a budget of €221183, wind turbines are included in the mix.

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4.2.2 AUA farm

The AUA farm only has an electrical demand that, simulated for an entire year, corresponds to 13.6 MWh. This makes it the reference farm with the lowest energy demand. According to the model, this farm has an LCC over 20 years of 46326, and yearly emits 2994 kg of GHG. As no thermal demand is present, simulation of PVT or solar thermal panels is irrelevant, as well of considering thermal storage. Only PV panels, electrical storage and wind energy are considered for this farm.

One wind turbine, with a nominal power of 15 kW and a cost of €60000, has the capacity to generate 22.9 MWh. Although this is less than it would produce in Belgium, it already exceeds the demands of the farm. This turbine would decrease the GHG emissions of the farm with 49.6%, but at the same time increase the LCC with 46.0%.

On the other hand, 1 kWp of PV panels yearly generates 1510 kWh, which is more than it would in Belgium. If entire wind turbine budget would be spent on PV panels, 328 m² could be installed. This could generate 70.7 kWh of electricity, reduce emissions with 45.8% and reduce LCC with 51.9%. It can be seen that these PV panels generate more electricity than a wind turbine, but still have a smaller GHG emission reduction because of the low self-consumption. Therefore, in the figure below, the combination of PV panels with an electrical battery was considered. The horizontal axis shows the investment in PV, while the remaining budget is spent on a battery. In all simulated case, the total budget is €60000.

Figure 16: Difference in LCC and GHG emissions for installations with PV panels and an electrical battery with a total budget of €60000, with indication of the results for a wind turbine.

It can be seen that the optimal LCC is obtained without battery. The emissions can however be reduced by using a battery in the mix. The optimal case is found where €31500 is spend on PV panels (154 m²) and adding a 47500-kWh battery. In this case, the emissions are reduced with 97.8%. Unfortunately, the LCC in this case increases with 54%.

For the AUA farm, an optimal RES system will likely include PV panels, assisted with electrical energy storage.

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5 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

To examine the sensitivity of the simulation results to the input parameters defined in chapter 2, the base case parameters were varied in a relevant range and the simulations presented in section 3.1 (the selected cases) are performed again. The parameters on which the sensitivity was studied are: the gas price, the electricity price, RES technology costs, the energy demand profile and the COP of the heat pump. The results are shown in Annex C Sensitivity analysis details. As the varied parameters have no or a limited impact on the GHG emissions, the presented results give the LCC for the different parameter values.

The results in chapter 3 showed that for some of the selected cases with a heat pump, the LCC is lower than that of a system with a gas boiler, while for others (depending on the added RES technologies), the LCC is higher. The results of the sensitivity analysis show that an increase in the gas price of 40% results in all heat pump cases the obtained LCC is lower than that of a system with a gas boiler. An increase of 10% is sufficient for a heat pump heating system (without other RES) to be competitive with a gas boiler. On the other hand, a reduction of the electricity price with 12.5% can result in the LCC of a heat pump system being lower than the LCC of a gas boiler system. The electricity price has a significant impact on the LCC. A reduction with 10% leads to an LCC reduction of 6.3% to 8.8% for the presented cases with a heat pump, and a reduction with 50% can even lead to an LCC reduction of 44.2%.

Next, the impact of the RES cost on the LCC was analysed by multiplying the investment cost of all RES with a factor between 0.5 and 1.5. The highest impact on the LCC of the RES investment cost is observed for case 5 (HP + PVT). Decreasing the RES cost with 50%, reduces the LCC over 20 years with 18.3%. For the case with only a heat pump, the effect is limited to 5.8%. This indicates that the largest part of the LCC is attributed to the operational costs, rather than the investments.

Next, the sensitivity of the model to the type of demand profile was investigated. For the electricity profile, the base case uses a demand profile where the required electrical power is averaged over an entire month. One alternative profile is available where the demand is varied with the ventilation flow rate of the farm. This results in a more realistic profile with peaks on hot days and reduced demand during the night. The results show that the effect of the profile for the LCC of the selected cases is limited (maximally +1.2%).

Finally, the (nominal) COP of the heat pumps was varied. If, e.g., by technology upgrades, the COP would be increased with 20%, the LCC of the selected cases decrease with 4.0% to 6.1%.

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6 OTHER TECHNOLOGIES

In addition to installing RES technologies for supplying the electrical and thermal energy demand, some other energy efficiency measures could be considered on a farm. In this chapter, some basic calculations will be performed to compare their potential to that of the RES discussed above. The considered technologies are:

- Electric tractors
- Building insulation
- Heat recovery from ventilation air

6.1 Electric tractors

For light duty work on a farm, electric tractors are currently penetrating the market. An review of the potential of electric tractors is given in Deliverable 2.1 [2]. Two examples that are given are the FT25G by Farmtrac and the Compact Electric Tractor by SOLETRACT. These both have 22 kWh battery pack, about 18 kW power, an autonomy of 3-6 hours and cost more or less €25000. In order to assess their potential for GHG emission reduction, they are compared to a conventional tractor with a diesel engine. An overview of the values used in the calculation are given in Table 3. It is assumed that the electric tractor uses it full capacity one time per day.

Table 3: Properties used for the comparison of an electric tractor with a conventional tractor.

	Electric tractor	Conventional tractor
Cost (€)	25000	12000
Energy supplied (kWh/day)	22	22
Engine efficiency (%)	90	40
Fuel cost (€/kWh)	0.28	0.2
GHG emissions (kg/kWh)	0.22	0.26
Lifetime (y)	10	20

Using the values from Table 3, the yearly GHG emissions and the LCC over 20 years can be calculated. The results are given in Table 4. It can be observed that the emissions are reduced with 62.5%, for an increase in LCC with 14%. This 3.26 ton/y reduction is however only 4.2% of the current GHG emissions related to heating and electricity. It should also be noted that the emissions and the LCC of the electric tractor are strongly dependent on the emissions and cost related to the electricity. Emissions of the grid are expected to reduce over time, and by used electricity from RES on site, the emissions and the LCC could be reduced further.

Table 4: Comparison of the GHG emissions and LCC for an electric tractor and a conventional tractor.

	Electric tractor	Conventional tractor
GHG emissions (ton/y)	1.96	5.22
LCC (€)	69334	60815

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6.2 Building insulation

Improving the insulation of a building will reduce the heating load during winter. When considering the ILVO reference farm, the high temperature heat load is approximately 138 kWh/y. This heating load consists partly of losses through the building envelope (conduction and infiltration losses) and heat losses with the exhaust ventilation air. The low temperature heat load (underfloor heating) or heating lamps are not taken into account, because the piglets will require this additional heating regardless of the level of insulation.

In order to evaluate the potential of insulation, detailed information about the composition of the heating loads, as well as properties of the building and costs of insulation are required. These are currently not available. A rough estimation will however be attempted for the ILVO farm. A building envelope loss area of 540 m² is considered (L: 74m, W: 34m, H: 2.5m). The prices for envelope improvement given in Deliverable 2.1 [2] range between 17 €/m² and 55 €/m². As there is no data on the composition of the heating load, it will be assumed that the envelop losses contribute 10% to 70% of the high temperature heating load.

With the values given above, simulations were performed starting from the base case (no other RES). Insulating the building. The results are given in Figure 17, where the GHG emissions or LCC of the reference case are indicated with the black dashed line. It can be observed that the GHG emissions are reduced with 4.5% to 31.7%, while the LCC can increase up to 2% or decrease up to 16.9%. Additionally, it should be noted that reducing the heat load by improving the building envelop will also allow the selection of smaller heating system, again reducing the LCC.

Figure 17: GHG emissions (left) and LCC (right) for various levels of insulation and insulation costs, with the values from the base case indicated with a black dashed line.

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6.3 Heat recovery from ventilation air

Another way to reduce the heating demand is by placing a heat exchanger between the fresh air and the exhaust air. This will preheat the air in winter, causing a reduction in the heat load. Additionally, it will cool the air in summer, allowing the ventilation flow rates to be reduced. Similar is with the building insulation, insufficient data is available for a thorough analysis of the impact of this technology on the emissions and costs. Therefore, a similar approach is used, where it is assumed that heat recovery can reduce the high temperature heating demand with 10% to 70%. In order to estimate the LCC, it was estimated that a heat recovery installation could cost between €10000 and €50000.

The results are given in Figure 18. As the assumptions are the same as for the insulation, the results for the GHG emissions are the same as in Figure 17. Also, the LCC results are similar.

Figure 18: GHG emissions (left) and LCC (right) for various levels of heat recovery and installation costs, with the values from the base case indicated with a black dashed line.

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7 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, the results of a simulation model of RES systems in livestock barns were presented. The goal of these simulations was to develop integrated RES solutions. The simulations were mainly applied on the ILVO reference farm in Belgium. However, the LVAT farm (Germany) and the AUA farm (Greece) were discussed as well.

The results indicate that when a farm has a high heating demand, switching from fossil fuels to a heat pump is the most effective way to reduce GHG emissions. Solely using a heat pump could however adversely impact the cost (evaluated by the life cycle cost, LCC). Therefore, additional measures should be taken. According to the model, the most cost-effective solution (especially where there is a high electrical demand, or where a heat pump is used) are PV-panels. When there is a high thermal demand, PVT or solar thermal collectors also appear in the mix of optimal solutions.

The results of the model also indicate that wind energy can be used to reduce emissions. This appears however only to be economical in combination with already a large amount of solar energy, which inevitably results in high investment costs. Additionally, while thermal energy storage appears to be very cost-effective in combination with solar collector and high thermal energy demands, electrical energy storage (batteries) should only be used when there is a large budget available and enough investments are made in solar or wind energy.

Finally, some measures to reduce emissions that are indirectly linked to the energy demand were evaluated. Electric tractors, building envelop insulation and energy recovery from exhaust air can all reduce the GHG emissions, sometimes in combination with financial gains. The levels of emission reductions are however smaller than the potential gains by e.g. implementing a heat pump. In future work, the use of the technologies could be investigated in more detail.

8 REFERENCES

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ANNEX A: INPUT DATA

A.1 Farm energy demand

The monthly energy demand for the ILVO reference farm can be seen in Figure 19. As mentioned in chapter 2, a profile for the heat demand on an hourly resolution was already available. For the electricity demand, this was not yet the case. Therefore, two options were investigated. Initially, the monthly electricity demand is spread uniformly over the entire month. Additionally, an alternative profile was developed where the electricity demand is scaled with the calculated ventilation flow rate [1], considering that the fans are the biggest electricity consumers. Both profiles are illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 19: Monthly energy demand for the ILVO reference barn

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Figure 20: Illustration of the two possible electricity demand profiles.

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A.2 Base case parameters

As can be deduced from the discussion on the implementation of the model, many parameters need to be specified before a simulation can start. In order to allow an easy comparison of the results, a base case was defined on which a sensitivity analysis is performed. An overview of all parameters, used for this base case, is given in Table 5:

Table 5: Input parameters used for the base case simulations.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Simulation time step	hour	1
Simulated period	hour	8760
Electricity cost	€/kWh	0.28
Electricity injection fee	€/kWh	0.8
Gas cost	€/kWh	0.1
GHG emissions elec. grid	kg/kWh	0.22
GHG emissions gas grid	kg/kWh	0.24
LCC period	year	20
LCC discount rate	%	6
Boiler efficiency	%	95
Low temperature heating	°C	40
High temperature heating	°C	60
Low temp. nom. COP	-	3.5
High temp. nom. COP	-	5
COP nominal temperature	°C	17
Initial battery charge	kWh	0
Initial thermal storage temp.	°C	40
Max. thermal storage temp.	°C	90
Boiler life span	year	15
Heat pump life span	year	20
PV panels life span	year	25
Solar collectors' life span	year	20
PVT panels life span	year	20
Wind turbine life span	year	20
Electrical battery life span	year	8
Thermal storage tank life span	year	20

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ANNEX B: TECHNOLOGY DETAILS

B.1 Heat pumps

When no gas boiler is present, a heat pump (HP) is used to heat the water. Air-sourced heat pumps are considered, which use electricity and heat extracted from the ambient air to heat the water. The performance of a heat pump is characterized by the coefficient of performance (COP), calculated with Eq. 2, where Q_h is the heat delivered to the water, Q_c is the heat extracted from the heat source (ambient air) and P_{comp} is the electricity used by the compressor:

$$COP = \frac{Q_h}{P_{comp}} = \frac{Q_h}{Q_h - Q_c} \quad (2)$$

A nominal COP (COP_n) at a nominal ambient temperature (T_n) is supplied to the model. The COP at different ambient temperatures (COP_i, T_i) is determined by keeping the same ratio to the theoretical maximal Carnot COP (Eq. 3):

$$COP_i = COP_n \cdot \frac{T_h - T_n}{T_h - T_i} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, T_h represents the temperature of the heat sink (= the water that is being heated).

It can be observed that in this simplified model, the performance of the heat pump is only depending on the ambient temperature and not on the delivered power.

Additionally, in order to be able to simulate other types of heat pumps, the model also allows to work with a fixed COP.

The investment cost attributed to the purchase of the heat pump is determined according to Figure 21 [1]. Although the cost of a heat pump increases with the heat pump capacity, the relative cost (€/kW) slightly decreases.

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Figure 21: Cost function of the heat pump [1].

B.2 Photovoltaic solar panels

The photovoltaic solar panels (PV) convert solar energy into electrical power. They are modelled in a way that the electricity production scales linearly with the irradiation data from the weather file. It is assumed that 7m² of PV panels corresponds to 1 kWp (kilowatt peak, or nominal power), which is obtained at an irradiation of 1000 W/m².

In a real installation, a converter is included in the installation to convert the generated electricity to a stable AC voltage. Although this converter typically has a certain (very high) efficiency, a start-up voltage and a maximum power, these non-idealities are not included in the simplified model. According to the model, and with the weather data from Belgium, an installation with a power of 1 kWp will annually yield 876 kWh. When the solar electricity generation is higher than the electricity demand (and the electrical storage is full), the remaining electricity is put on the grid and an injection fee is received.

The investment cost for PV panels is given in Figure 22, together with the costs for thermal solar collectors and PVT-panels (which are discussed next). These cost functions are derived from information gather from different online sources and can vary country per country.

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Figure 22: Cost function of the different types of solar panels.

The monthly electrical energy generated by the PV panels located on the ILVO is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Monthly electrical energy generated by PV panels on the ILVO farm.

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B.3 Thermal solar collectors

Solar thermal panels (ST) directly convert solar radiation into heat. Different types of solar collectors exist with efficiencies depending on the operating temperatures. For this simplified model, the solar collectors have a fixed efficiency, independent of the operating temperature. They capture four times as much energy as a photovoltaic solar panel, which would correspond to a thermal power output of 571 W for 1 m² of solar collectors for an irradiation of 1000 W/m². Since typically no grid is present to which heat can be injected, excess heat produced is considered wasted (in the case of no or insufficient thermal energy storage).

The implemented cost function for solar collectors is shown in Figure 22.

B.4 Photovoltaic-thermal solar panels

In addition to photovoltaic solar panels (PV) and solar thermal collectors (ST), photovoltaic-thermal panels (PVT) exist which produce both heat and electricity. Although they are considered less efficient both for heat and electricity than PV and ST panels, their combined efficiency is higher. They are modelled as generating a given fraction of the electricity from a PV installation with the same size and a given fraction of the heat from a ST installation with the same size. For the simulations performed in this report, it is assumed that they have 80% of the efficiency of PV panels and 70% of the efficiency of ST panels.

In Figure 22, their cost function can be observed as well.

B.5 Wind energy

In addition to solar energy, wind energy was also implemented the model. Wind turbines come in different shapes and a large range of sizes. For this study, small horizontal axis wind turbines (with an axis height of maximally 15m) are used, as these are considered most relevant for farming applications.

A horizontal axis wind turbine, specifically targeted at farming applications, was implemented in the model [4]. This windmill has a nominal power of 15 kW at a nominal wind speed of 7.8 m/s. According to the manufacturer, the annual energy yield for Belgium should be between 30 MWh and 46 MWh. The wind turbine has a cut-in and cut-out velocity of 2.5 m/s and 20 m/s respectively. The generated electrical power (P) is dependent on the wind velocity (v) with a relationship given in Eq. 4, with subscript n indicating nominal values.

$$P = P_n \cdot \left(\frac{v}{v_n}\right)^3 \quad (4)$$

The wind velocities in the weather file are given for a height of 10 m. When these are multiplied by a factor of 1.3 to take the height difference into account, the wind turbine in the model has an annual yield of 35 MWh.

An investment cost of €60000 was considered realistic for the wind turbine. When a system design with a different nominal wind turbine power is simulated, a cost scaled linearly with the nominal power is considered.

The distribution of the wind velocity on the ILVO farm and the corresponding monthly electricity yield for the 15 kWn wind turbine are illustrated in Figure 24 and 25.

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Figure 24: Distribution of the wind velocity at 15 m on the ILVO farm.

Figure 25: Monthly electrical energy generated by the 15 kWn wind turbine on the ILVO farm.

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B.6 Electrical energy storage

When instantaneous electricity generation exceeds the electrical energy demand, it can be injected to the grid. As injection fees are typically much lower than the electricity cost, it is economically usually more interesting to store the electricity. For this storage, an electrical battery is modelled. This battery has a given capacity (kWh) and a maximal electrical power (both for charging and discharging) (kW). Although both can be entered individually in the model, the power is for most simulations selected in such a way that the battery can be fully (dis-)charged in 2 hours, as electrical power usually increases when capacity increases. The maximal power of the battery is considered independent of the state of charge. The capacity of the battery is furthermore fully available (no *depth of discharge*).

The cost function for the electrical batteries (based on various online sources) is given in Figure 26:

Figure 26: Cost function for electrical energy storage.

B.7 Thermal energy storage

Similar to electrical energy, thermal energy generation can exceed heat demand. In this case, the surplus heat can be stored. This thermal energy storage is modelled as a water tank of a given volume that can be heated. The tank is considered to have a uniform temperature (no stratification) for simplicity reasons. The maximal thermal power that can be (dis-)charged in (or from) tank can be specified by the user of the model. However, for the simulations in this report, this thermal power is corresponding to a complete (dis-)charge of the tank in two hours. In addition to the tank volume and the maximal thermal power, also the maximal temperature (90°C for the simulations in this report) needs to be specified. Thermal losses to the environment are not considered for simplicity.

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The cost function for the thermal storage water tanks (based on various online sources) is given in Figure 27:

Figure 27: Cost function for thermal energy storage.

B.8 Condensing gas boiler

When a system is simulated where no heat pumps are present and the solar heat generation is not sufficient to cover the heating loads, a condensing gas boiler is considered. The boiler combusts gas from the grid to heat the water. The boiler is modelled with a constant efficiency of 95% and has a fixed cost of €15000.

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ANNEX C: SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS DETAILS

C.1 Energy price

Figure 28: Sensitivity of the LCC for the different cases to the gas price.

Figure 29: Sensitivity of the LCC for the different cases to the electricity price.

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C.2 RES technology cost

Figure 30: Sensitivity of the LCC for the different cases to the RES investment cost.

C.3 Energy demand profile

Figure 31: Sensitivity of the LCC for the different cases to energy demand profile.

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C.4 Heat pump COP

Figure 32: Sensitivity of the LCC for the different cases to the heat pump COP.

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ANNEX D: INDIVIDUAL RES COMPARISON WITHOUT HEAT PUMP

In section 3.2, a comparison was made between PV panels, solar collectors (ST, solar thermal) and PVT on the one hand, and between solar energy and wind energy on the other hand. This comparison was done for a farm with a heat pump. This annex presents the results of the same simulations, but for a farm with a gas boiler. Figures 33 and 34 show that PV panels still result in the lowest LCC (right graphs). For GHG emission reductions (left graphs), PVT becomes most interesting. In contrast to with a heat pump, solar thermal collector results now in a higher GHG emission reduction. It can also be noted that for large available roof areas, an optimal combination of PV panels and solar collectors can be found (regarding emissions). The results regarding the wind turbines can be seen in Figures 35 and 36. Except for the reduced potential for emission reductions compared to the heat pump case, no significant differences can be observed.

Figure 33: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and solar collectors for a farm without heat pump (0: all ST, 1: all PV).

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Figure 34: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and PVT panels for a farm without heat pump (0: all PVT, 1: all PV).

Figure 35: Comparison of GHG emission reduction and LCC for various areas of PV panels and one to three wind turbines for a farm without heat pump.

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Figure 36: GHG emission reduction and life cycle cost for a combination of PV panels and wind turbines for a farm without heat pump.